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Abstract [En]: This paper examines the landmark ruling of the ECOWAS Court of Justice in *Obianuju Udeh & Others v. Republic of Nigeria*, which held the Nigerian government accountable for human rights violations during the 2020 #EndSARS protests. The Court determined that Nigeria breached key provisions of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, including the right not to be subjected to inhuman treatment, the right to security, the freedom of expression and assembly. The analysis delves into the reparations awarded to the victims, emphasizing the significance of state accountability and the imperative for systemic reforms to prevent future violations, thereby advancing the regional framework for human rights protection.

Titolo: La responsabilità del governo nigeriano per le violazioni dei diritti umani durante le proteste #EndSARS: un'analisi della sentenza della Corte ECOWAS

Abstract [It]: Questo articolo esamina la storica sentenza della Corte di Giustizia della CEDEAO nel caso *Obianuju Udeh & altri c. Repubblica della Nigeria*, che ha ritenuto il governo nigeriano responsabile di violazioni dei diritti umani durante le proteste #EndSARS del 2020. La Corte ha stabilito che la Nigeria ha violato disposizioni fondamentali della Carta Africana dei Diritti dell'Uomo e dei Popoli, tra cui il diritto a non essere sottoposti a trattamenti inumani e degradanti, diritto alla sicurezza, alla libertà di espressione e di assemblea. L'analisi approfondisce le riparazioni assegnate alle vittime, sottolineando l'importanza della responsabilità statale e l'urgenza di riforme sistemiche per prevenire future violazioni, contribuendo così al rafforzamento del quadro regionale di tutela dei diritti umani.

Parole chiave: Corte ECOWAS, Nigeria, Proteste EndSARS, Libertà di espressione.

Keywords: ECOWAS court, Nigeria, EndSARS protest, right to freedom of expression.

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Nota a [Obianuju Catherine Udeh and Another v Federal Republic of Nigeria \(ECW/CC.J/APP/72/21; ECW/CCJ/JUD/29/24\) \[2024\] ECOWASCJ 1 \(10 July 2024\)](#)

* Articolo sottoposto a referaggio.

1. Introduction

In *Obianuju Udeb, Perpetual Kamsi, and Dabiraoluwa Adeyinka v. Republic of Nigeria* (10 July 2024), the ECOWAS Court of Justice addressed the Nigerian government's role in the violations of human rights during the #EndSARS protests of 2020. This landmark case arose from the applicants' allegations of physical and emotional harm due to the excessive force used by Nigerian security forces to disperse peaceful protestors calling for the disbandment of the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS).¹

The plaintiffs argued that the Nigerian authorities' actions breached fundamental rights protected under the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR), including the right to life, freedom from torture, security, and the right to assembly and association. The court ruled in favour of the applicants, finding Nigeria responsible for failing to prevent and investigate abuses committed by its forces, and for unnecessary and unproportionate use of force. This decision reinforces ECOWAS's commitment to protecting human rights within member states and emphasizes the importance of accountability in governmental responses to civil dissent.

The judgment has significant implications, not only for Nigeria but also for broader West African legal standards on state obligations to protect citizens during public protests. By awarding damages and mandating a government investigation, the court's decision underscores the region's evolving jurisprudence on state accountability and human rights.

2. Summary of facts and allegations

In *Obianuju & Others v. Republic of Nigeria*, the applicants, three women involved in Nigeria's 2020 #EndSARS protests, alleged serious human rights violations, including physical harm, psychological trauma, and the violation of their rights to life, right not to be subjected to inhuman treatment, security, and freedom of assembly. They claimed that Nigerian security forces used excessive force against peaceful protesters and failed to investigate abuses, seeking damages and official accountability.²

The #EndSARS protests, which peaked in October 2020, were primarily driven by widespread allegations of police brutality and human rights abuses by the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS), a notorious unit

¹ The ECOWAS Court of Justice is a principal judicial organ of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), established in 1991 to resolve disputes related to the interpretation and application of ECOWAS treaties, protocols, and conventions. Over time, its mandate expanded to include jurisdiction over human rights cases, a development that significantly strengthened its role in promoting accountability and justice within the region. The Court has the power to hear cases brought by individuals, civil society organizations, and other entities alleging violations of human rights by ECOWAS member states. Unlike many other regional human rights systems, individuals do not need to exhaust domestic remedies before filing a complaint with the ECOWAS Court. The Court can order both monetary and non-monetary reparations, including compensation, guarantees of non-repetition, and directives for states to reform laws or policies. On its human rights jurisdiction, see also F. VONA, *La Corte dell'ECOWAS chiarisce la portata della propria giurisdizione in materia di diritti umani con una storica pronuncia sulla libertà di espressione in Gambia*, in *Federalismi.it*, 2018.

² See also the 2016 report by [Amnesty International](https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/AFR11/001/201601/), amicus curiae of this case.

within the Nigerian police force.³ Originally created to address robbery and violent crime, SARS developed a reputation for excessive force, extortion, illegal detention, torture, and extrajudicial killings. Videos and testimonies shared on social media fuelled public outrage and mobilized thousands of young Nigerians to demand the disbanding of SARS and broader police reforms.

The protests were peaceful but met with significant resistance from Nigerian security forces, leading to violent crackdowns. The situation escalated tragically on October 20, 2020, when Nigerian soldiers allegedly opened fire on protesters at the Lekki Toll Gate in Lagos, resulting in casualties that many refer to as the “Lekki Massacre”.⁴ This event galvanized international attention and condemnation and led to further scrutiny of the Nigerian government’s handling of human rights issues.

The applicants were both present at the Lekki Toll Gate shootings. The first applicant, after having sought cover, live-streamed the shooting on her Instagram account. In her application before the Court, she states that, after the 20 of October 2020, she received threatening phone menaces because of the live-streamed video, and she was forced to hide for eleven months and finally leave the country to seek asylum.⁵ The second applicant witnessed soldiers collecting and loading the protesters’ corpses in their trucks after the shootings, and was threatened by soldiers whilst providing first aid to the people who needed it. The third applicant also witnessed shootings, and on one occasion she was almost hit by a bullet that was shot directly at her.

Therefore, the applicants sought redress for the violation of their rights protected by international law instruments, namely the African Charter on Human and People’s Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the Universal Declaration on Human Rights and the UN Convention Against Torture.

The violations that the Respondent needed to address, according to the Applicant, concerned several fundamental human rights protected by the above-mentioned instruments. They claimed that Nigerian security forces used excessive force against peaceful protesters and failed to investigate abuses, seeking damages and official accountability.

The applicants sought multiple remedies, including official declarations that the Respondent violated their fundamental human rights, causing them psychological trauma, and failed to investigate, arrest, or prosecute those responsible for the 2020 Lekki Toll Gate shootings. They requested that the ECOWAS Court compel the Respondent to adopt measures to prevent future violations, along with reparations of 50 million Naira for each applicant and witness for the abuses they suffered. Additionally, they demanded

³ A. S. OGBETTE, M. O. IDAM, A. O. KAREEM, *An overview of the impact of special anti-robbery squad (SARS) in Nigeria*, in *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 8(4), 2018, pp. 180-187.

⁴ E. CHUKWUEMEKA, *The October 2020# EndSARS Protest and the Transformation of the Nigerian State* in *Journal of Political Science and International Relations*, 12(2), 2023, pp. 16-29.

⁵ *Obianuju & others v. Republic of Nigeria* § 29.

200 million Naira in punitive damages due to the government's failure to control its agents' actions at the Lekki Toll Gate.⁶

3. The Republic of Nigeria's counterarguments

The Nigerian government, as the Respondent, contested the allegations of human rights violations arising from the #EndSARS protests. The government asserted that the applicants' participation in the protests was unlawful, arguing that the demonstrations at the Lekki Toll Gate on October 20, 2020, were organized under the pretence of peacefully protesting against police brutality, but as a matter of fact, they were not conducted peacefully. The respondent claimed that its agents, including the military and police forces, adhered to strict engagement protocols without resorting to excessive or lethal force, thus denying any responsibility for harm to the protesters.

The government also contended that the presence of the soldiers at the protest site was solely to restore order and ensure public safety. It accused the applicants of incitement and aiding violence, with the first applicant allegedly using social media to stir disaffection toward law enforcement, while the second and third applicants were said to have supported the protests through logistical coordination, allegedly exacerbating the unrest.⁷ The respondent argued that there was insufficient evidence to substantiate the applicants' claims, particularly regarding the alleged violation of their rights to life and security of person.

1. Proceedings before the Court and Merits

After confirming the eligibility and admissibility of the claim in order to establish jurisdiction over the application, the Court reviewed a report from the Amicus Curiae, Amnesty International.⁸ This report was submitted under Article 89 of the Rules of the Community Court of Justice. The Court accepted the report, recognizing it as a valuable contribution to understanding specific fundamental human rights issues rather than a direct claim of rights violations. As Amicus Curiae, Amnesty International was not a party to the case and thus could not seek monetary relief; its role was limited to providing impartial expertise to assist the Court's deliberations.

After, the Court proceeded with the analysis of whether the Respondent's actions constituted a violation of the rights of life, existence, and security of the person of the Applicants, protected by Articles 4 and 6 of the ACHPR.

⁶ Idem, § 38 letters a-m.

⁷ In response to the specific allegations of each of the applicants, the Respondent argued that the Applicants' actions, including the live streaming on Instagram of the first applicant, had the objective of "establish disaffection against law enforcement agents" and "to invite more hoodlums nationwide to join in the unlawful protest" (§42, §45)

⁸ On the role of amicus curiae in international court proceedings, see also A. WIJK, *Amicus Curiae before International Courts and Tribunals*, Nomos Verlagsgesellschaft, Baden-Baden, 2018; A. DI MAIO, Il ruolo dell'amicus curiae nella funzione giurisdizionale: evoluzioni e prospettive, in A. ODDENINO, E. RUOZZI, A. VITERBO, F. COSTAMAGNA, L.MOLA, L. POLI (eds), *La funzione giurisdizionale nell'ordinamento internazionale e nell'ordinamento comunitario*, ESI, Napoli, 2010.

Regarding the right to life, the Court determined that the Respondent did not violate this right. The Court emphasized that a successful claim for a right-to-life violation requires evidence showing that life has been directly taken.⁹ In this case, while the Applicants provided evidence suggesting that protestors' lives were lost during the October 20 protests, the claim was filed solely on behalf of the living applicants, not the deceased. Consequently, the Court could not establish a breach of Article 4 of the ACHPR but instructed the Respondent to "investigate the claims of arbitrary killings of citizens."¹⁰

With regard to the violation of article 6 ACHPR, the Court established that the Republic of Nigeria violated such right. As the Court already established in *Mohamed Morlu v. Republic of Sierra Leone*, the right to security of the person requires the State to protect the physical integrity of citizens from abuse of official authorities. The Court noted that the evidence produced by the Applicants shows that the protest was peaceful until the arrival of the Government's agents who started shooting. Therefore, there was no evidence of violence before the actual arrival of the Respondent's armed forces. The Court found that the shootings caused harm and that the Respondent's use of force was contrary to the principle of necessity and proportionality, resulting in a violation of Article 6 ACHPR.

Subsequently, the Court analysed whether the Applicants had been victims of torture, inhumane and degrading treatments concerning physical, emotional and psychological abuses they were supposedly subjected to at the hand of the Respondent's agents in their extrajudicial attacks. The Court, in analysing these merits, adopted a wide definition of cruel, inhuman and degrading treatments, which encompasses "the widest possible array of physical and mental stress".¹¹ As established by the Inter-American Court of Human Rights in *Loayza-Tamayo v. Peru* (1997), violations of an individual's physical and psychological integrity encompass various forms of cruel, inhuman, and degrading treatment. Such violations occur due to the actions of a public officer, and each instance requires specific evidence tailored to the particular circumstances. This principle underlines that proving these violations demands a close examination of both the nature of the harm and the specific actions that caused it, ensuring that accountability for physical and psychological harm rests on concrete and contextualized evidence. After the examination of the evidence produced by the Applicants, comprising audiovisual material, the Court concluded that such evidence constituted sufficient probative value.¹² The Court concluded that the Respondent was in breach of Article 5 of the ACHPR.

⁹ As it had previously established in the case *Mamadou Mouhtar Baldé v. Republic of Guinea*, Judgement No. ECW/CCJ/JUD/52/23.

¹⁰ §100.

¹¹ §118.

¹² "In the instance of an allegation of torture in the context of a protest by civilians, the Court is compelled to find that an area controlled by security agents of the Respondent (who are heavily armed and shooting) supported by evidence, is a breach of Article 5 of the ACHPR", § 125.

With the regard to the right to freedom of expression under the ACHPR, the Court declared a breach of Articles 9, 10 and 11. The Court examined the evidence provided by the Applicants, namely videos recorded during nighttime and daytime. The first recording showed peaceful protests, while in the second there were gunshots, footings of wounded people and bodies covered in blood. In adjudicating whether the behaviour of the State's armed forces corresponded to a violation of the right of freedom of expression under the ACHPR, the Court relied on Principle 5(a) of the United Nations Basic Principles on the Use of Force and Firearms by Law Enforcement Officials.¹³ Based on the evidence concerning the disproportionate use of force implied to disperse the peaceful protest, the Court found that the Respondent was in breach of Article 11 ACHPR. Moreover, the Court provided that the Respondent "failed to allow them [the Applicants] basic guarantee to express them peacefully",¹⁴ constituting a breach of Article 9 ACHPR. Finally, with regard to Article 10 ACHPR, and because of what has been affirmed in this paragraph, the Court found that the Respondent had breached its obligation to guarantee the right to assemble freely.

The Court then considered whether the Respondent had violated its obligations under Article 1 of the ACPHR, namely its obligations to investigate human rights violations. In fact, despite the Respondent had set up a quasi-judicial mechanism through the institution of a Panel set up by the Lagos State Government regarding the Lekki Toll Gate shootings, the Panel's recommendations had not been put into practice, and the agents prosecuted. The Court noted that the matter at hand was indeed whether the violators had been effectively prosecuted, and it held that "the failure of the Respondent to adduce evidence on the steps it has taken to discharge its obligations warrants the Court to declare that it has failed in its duty under Article 1 of the ACHPR ... Consequently, the Court declares that the Respondent has failed in its duty to investigate human rights violations".¹⁵

Finally, the Court asserted whether the Applicants had been denied the right to an effective remedy protected under Article 2 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. It noted that the right to an effective remedy it is not enshrined explicitly in the ACHPR, but it can be derived from Article 1 since it imposes an obligation on Member States to respect and promote human rights. Furthermore, as the Court established in the cases *Jawara v. Gambia* 147/95 and 149/96, remedies are considered to be available when they can be pursued without impediment, they are considered effective when they offer a prospective of success, and they are deemed sufficient when they are capable of redressing the complaint.¹⁶ In the case at hand, the Court concluded that the establishment of the previously discussed

¹³ "Whenever the lawful use of force and firearms is unavoidable, law enforcement officials shall: (a) Exercise restraint in such use and act in proportion to the seriousness of the offence and the legitimate objective to be achieved".

¹⁴ § 138.

¹⁵ § 153

¹⁶ § 157.

panel did not suffice to demonstrate that the Applicants were provided with an effective remedy for the violations they endured. This insufficiency was further underscored by the Respondent's rejection of the panel's recommendations, undermining the remedial process and its capacity to address the Applicants' grievances meaningfully.

4. Reparations

The Court determined that the Respondent had violated several human rights protected under the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR). As reparations, the Court ordered monetary compensation for the victims and mandated the Respondent to conduct a new investigation and prosecute those responsible for the violations. Specifically, the Court awarded each applicant a sum of two million Naira (approximately €1,100) for each violation, which included breaches of the right to personal security, the prohibition of torture, the right to freedom of expression, the State's duty to investigate, and the right to an effective remedy. This structured approach to compensation underscores the severity and multiplicity of the violations committed.

The Court failed to capitalise on an opportunity to implement non-monetary reparations, which could have played a crucial role in addressing the systemic nature of the violations in question. In contrast to financial compensation, non-monetary reparations—such as guarantees of non-repetition, public apologies, memorialisation, and institutional reforms—serve a restorative function that extends beyond addressing individual harm. Furthermore, they contribute to social healing, institutional accountability, and prevention of future violations.

The absence of non-monetary measures is particularly significant in this case, as the violence associated with the #EndSARS protests, especially at the Lekki Toll Gate, reflects deeper structural issues in Nigeria's policing system. The problem was not limited to a single incident of excessive use of force but was indicative of a broader pattern of abuse attributed to SARS. Given this context, guarantees of non-repetition, such as police reform, the establishment of oversight mechanisms, and human rights training for law enforcement, would have addressed the root causes of the violations.

Comparatively, other international courts have recommended non-monetary reparations that addressed broad questions of justice within the affected country. For instance, the Inter-American Court of Human Rights (IACtHR) has frequently emphasized the importance of non-monetary reparations alongside financial compensation. In *Velásquez Rodríguez v. Honduras* (1988), the IACtHR ordered the State to investigate human rights violations and prosecute those responsible as part of a guarantee of non-repetition.¹⁷ Similarly, in *Barrios Altos v. Peru* (2001), the Court demanded the annulment of amnesty laws

¹⁷ Inter-American Court of Human Rights, *Case of Velásquez-Rodríguez v. Honduras*, Judgment of July 29, 1988.

shielding perpetrators from accountability as a measure to prevent future violations.¹⁸ These cases highlight the role of institutional reform in ensuring justice and non-recurrence.

The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) has also advocated for non-monetary measures of reparation. In *Öcalan v. Turkey* (2005), the ECtHR recommended Turkey to provide a fair trial as a remedial measure.¹⁹ Likewise, in *Sejdić and Finci v. Bosnia and Herzegovina* (2009), the Court required legislative changes to eliminate discriminatory practices ensuring that all citizens, regardless of their ethnic background, could participate equally in political processes.²⁰

The African human rights system, encompassing the African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights and the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights, has employed non-monetary remedies extensively, often complementing monetary compensation with structural or systemic reforms. These remedies reflect the African system's commitment to addressing not only individual harm but also the broader causes of human rights violations. One notable example is the *Ogiek Case v. Kenya*, wherein the African Court mandated the Kenyan government to recognise and title the ancestral lands of the Ogiek people.²¹ This decision was significant as it emphasised restitution and the protection of collective cultural and land rights. Beyond individual compensation, the Court stipulated that territorial demarcation and delimitation should be realized in accordance with national laws, through an administrative or legislative act. As a non-monetary reparatory measure, the Court mandated that the respondent State formally recognise the Ogiek Community as an Indigenous people and implement measures to safeguard their language, culture, and religious practices. In accordance with their status as an Indigenous people, the Ogiek must be consulted prior to the implementation of any development or conservation projects affecting their ancestral lands. The Court stipulated that the Ogiek's right to consultation must be effectual, actively engaging the Indigenous community. Such consultations should be conducted in good faith and in a manner that respects the traditions, culture, and religious practices of the Ogiek. During these consultations, the respondent State must acknowledge the Ogiek people's right to freely express their prior, informed consent for any decision impacting their ancestral lands and community life.²²

Similarly, in *Media Rights Agenda and Others v. Nigeria* (2000), the African Commission highlighted the structural nature of certain violations by recommending legal reforms. The case involved restrictions on

¹⁸ Inter-American Court of Human Rights, *Case of Barrios Altos v. Peru*, Judgment of March 14, 2001.

¹⁹ European Court of Human Rights, *Case of Öcalan v. Turkey* (Application no. 46221/99) Judgement of 12 May 2005.

²⁰ European Court of Human Rights, *Sejdić and Finci v. Bosnia and Herzegovina* (Applications nos. 27996/06 and 34836/06), Judgement of 22 December 2009.

²¹ African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights, *Application 006/2012 - The African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights vs Republic of Kenya* (2022).

²² See also: L. ZUCCARI, *La Corte africana stabilisce le misure riparatorie a favore del popolo indigeno degli Ogiek. Caso chiuso?*, in *Federalismi.it*, n. 21, 2022, pp. 231-242; G. GIACOMINI, *Human Rights Violations in the name of environmental protection: reflections on the reparations owed to the Ogiek Indigenous people of Kenya*, in *Ordine Internazionale e Diritti Umani*, 2023, pp. 508-520.

press freedom, and the Commission called for the repeal of repressive laws and constitutional amendments to align national laws with international human rights standards.²³ This case demonstrates how non-monetary remedies can facilitate legislative changes to safeguard rights.

These decisions reflect a broader trend in the African human rights system, where non-monetary remedies such as guarantees of non-repetition, legislative reforms, and cultural restitution are central to achieving justice. These measures align with international human rights jurisprudence, such as cases from the Inter-American and European systems, where structural remedies are frequently employed to address systemic injustices and prevent recurrence. The African system's emphasis on non-monetary remedies demonstrates a nuanced understanding of human rights violations and the need for comprehensive, multifaceted solutions.

Had the ECOWAS Court incorporated such measures in this case, it could have strengthened its judgment by addressing the systemic issues underlying the violations. This could have included compelling Nigeria to formally guarantee non-repetition through institutional reforms, improved oversight of security forces, and public acknowledgement of wrongdoing. Such steps align with international human rights jurisprudence and reinforce the preventive function of human rights courts, as demonstrated in the previous paragraphs.

5. Conclusions

The case of *Obianuju Udeh, Perpetual Kamsi, and Dabiraoluwa Adeyinka v. Republic of Nigeria* represents a pivotal moment in the jurisprudence of the ECOWAS Court of Justice. By addressing the Nigerian government's responsibility for human rights violations during the #EndSARS protests, the Court underscored the importance of accountability, proportionality in the use of force, and the protection of fundamental freedoms.

The judgment affirmed that the rights to security, freedom from torture, and freedoms of expression and assembly, as enshrined in the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, are inviolable even in the face of public dissent. In its decision, the Court emphasized the state's obligation to investigate and prosecute human rights violations, thereby reinforcing the principle that impunity for state agents cannot be tolerated. The present article has highlighted that the reparations awarded, while primarily monetary, underscore the need for a more holistic approach to justice, incorporating non-monetary remedies to address systemic failings and prevent recurrence.

²³ African Commission on Human and People's Rights, *Media Rights Agenda and Others v. Nigeria*, Comm. Nos. 105/93, 128/94, 130/94 and 152/96 (1998).

This case contributes significantly to the evolving landscape of regional human rights protection in West Africa, setting a precedent for stronger enforcement of state obligations. It also highlights the critical role of international human rights bodies in supporting victims and ensuring accountability, even when national mechanisms fall short. As such, the ECOWAS Court’s ruling is not only a victory for the applicants but also a call to action for member states to uphold the principles of justice, accountability, and human rights in their governance.